

A NEW SYNTHESIS OF *cis*-8-METHYLHYDRINDANONE-1

BY RAMESH CHANDRA CHATTERJEE AND BIDYUT KAMAL BHATTACHARYYA

A new synthesis of *cis*-8-methylhydrindanone-1 has been described.

In the classical synthesis of equilenin, Johnson and his co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2942) built up the cyclopentane ring from 1-keto-2-methyl-2-cyano-7-methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrophenanthrene by the Stobbe condensation with dimethyl succinate. Attempts to apply this reaction with other similar systems resulted either in cleavage of the ring containing the nitrile or the elimination of carbomethoxy group (*ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 1426; 1952, **74**, 2832; "Organic Reactions", Vol. VI, p. 13).

In order to circumvent the above difficulties in the Stobbe-Johnson reaction, an attempt in the following line was made to obtain the desired propionic acid chain, keeping the carbomethoxy group at 2-position intact (cf. *Science & Culture*, 1956, **21**, 543).

Ethyl 2-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (I: R = Me; R₁ = CO₂Et) underwent the Knoevenagel condensation with ethyl cyanoacetate by the procedure of Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 3452) as modified by Ciagoe *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, **15**, 381) to furnish ethyl 2-methyl-2-carbomethoxycyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetate (II: R = Me; R₁ = CO₂Et) in 60-66% yield. This compound was previously prepared by Linstead and Millidge (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 478) in poor yield.

During the afore-mentioned condensation, a solid byproduct has been obtained which is resistant to acid hydrolysis but can be hydrolysed with 20% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (Kon and Thorpe, *ibid.*, 1919, 115, 686; Paul, this *Journal*, 1931, **8**, 717) to furnish the unsaturated dicarboxylic acid (XVI: m.p. 169°) which is the β-acid of Bachmann and Kushner (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1963). The authentic sample of the dicarboxylic acid (XVI) has been prepared from the unsaturated cyano-ester (II: R = Me; R₁ = CO₂Et) by hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid. The structure (III) has been assigned to the byproduct on the basis of the above evidence and its ultra-violet data (*Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **42**, 105; Woodward, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **63**, 1123; 1942, **64**, 72, 76; cf. Banerjee *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 1516; Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1953, **30**, 443; Chaudhuri and Mukharji, *ibid.*, 1956, **33**, 155).

The unsaturated cyano-ester (II: R = Me; R₁ = CO₂Et) was then condensed with ethyl bromoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide according to the procedure of Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 3458) to yield diethyl α-cyano-α-(2-methyl-2-carbomethoxycyclohex-Δ^{2,3}-enyl)-succinate (IV: R = Me; R₁ = R₄ = CO₂Et; R₂ = Et; R₃ = CN). The latter compound on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid yielded either a mixture of acids (A: m.p. 152-53°) and (B: m.p. 184-85°) or an oily mixture of acids (A) and (B) containing a solid acid (C: m.p. 200°) depending upon the period of heating. The gummy acidic residue left after fractional crystallisation was esterified to furnish a mixture of the neutral tri-ester (IV: R = R₂ = Me; R₁ = R₄ = CO₂Me; R₃ = H) and the lactonic di-ester (V: R = Me; R₁ = R₂ = CO₂Me).

The acid (A) could be converted by treatment with diazomethane into the above neutral ester and the latter could be saponified back to the acid (A), which from its analytical and neutral equivalent data should have the structure (IV: $R=Me$; $R_1=R_4=CO_2H$; $R_2=R_3=H$). Further, the acid (A) could be converted, in poor yield, either into the acid (B) or the acid (C), depending on the period of heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid.

The above-mentioned lactonic di-ester was saponified to the acid (B) which could again be esterified with diazomethane to the same ester. The latter on treatment with sodium methoxide in methanol and methyl iodide, followed by treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid, yielded the tri-ester (IV: $R=R_2=Me$; $R_1=R_4=CO_2Me$; $R_3=H$). Hence, the probable structure (V: $R=Me$; $R_1=R_2=CO_2H$) may be assigned to the acid (B).

The acid (C) from its neutral equivalent and conversion to the methyl ester with diazomethane has been found to be a lactonic monocarboxylic acid and may have any one of the structures (V: $R=Me$; $R_1=CO_2H$; $R_2=H$ and $R=Me$; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CO_2H$); (X: $R=Me$; $R_1=CO_2H$; $R_2=H$ and $R=Me$; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CO_2H$); (XII) and (XIII). It was treated with phosphorus pentachloride followed by alcohol and the crude chloro compound, thus formed, was then heated with zinc and acetic acid (Mukherji, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 449), but the result was unpromising. The chloro-ester was next refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (10, 25 and 40%) to get the unsaturated dicarboxylic acid, but unfortunately a resinous material was obtained in each case. Finally, a methanolic solution of the acid (C) on treatment with sodium methoxide and methyl iodide yielded a hydroxy-ester which on dehydration with fused potassium hydrogen sulphate, followed by hydrogenation, furnished a saturated di-ester. The latter on hydrolysis furnished a dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 156° which may have either the structure (XVII: $R=Me$; $R_1=CO_2H$; $R_2=R_3=H$) or (XIV: $R=R_1=H$). Both the *cis*- and *trans*-forms of the acid (XVII: $R=Me$; $R_1=CO_2H$; $R_2=R_3=H$) have been prepared by Johnson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 215); the *cis*-acid, m.p. $108-109^\circ$, and the *trans*-acid, m.p. $179-80^\circ$. Hence, the above di-acid should have the structure (XIV: $R=R_1=H$), the authentic specimen of which was prepared as follows:

A Stobbe condensation was carried out with 2-methylcyclohexanone and dimethyl succinate in presence of potassium *tert*-butoxide to yield β -carbomethoxy- β -(2-methylcyclohexenyl)-propionic acid (XV: $R=H$) in 71% yield (cf. Cook and Phillip, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 162). The latter on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid furnished the lactonic monocarboxylic acid (V: $R=Me$; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CO_2H$), m.p. 107° . This lactonic acid was also synthesised by the condensation of ethyl 2-methylcyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetate (II: $R=Me$; $R_1=H$) with ethyl bromoacetate, followed by hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The acid (V: $R=Me$; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CO_2H$) on pyrolysis at $250-60^\circ$ yielded a neutral lactone (V: $R=Me$; $R_1=R_2=H$), which was also prepared by Bachmann and Raunio (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2530). It might be pointed out that the acid (C) did not undergo decarboxylation under the same condition. The synthesis of the acid (V: $R=Me$; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CO_2H$) excluded the latter structure for the acid (C). The half-ester (XV: $R=H$) was esterified

with diazomethane to yield the di-ester (XV: R=Me) which on hydrogenation, followed by alkaline hydrolysis, furnished the dicarboxylic acid (XIV: R=R₁=H), identical with the acid obtained from (C). This ruled out the structures (X: R=Me; R₁=CO₂H; R₂=H) and (V: R=Me; R₁=CO₂H; R₂=H) for the parent lactonic acid (C). Moreover, the acid (V: R=Me; R₁=CO₂H; R₂=H) was prepared by Bachmann and Raunio (*loc.cit.*). The structures (X: R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CO₂H) and (VI: R=Me; R₁=R₂=H) were also excluded by the observation that the afore-mentioned hydroxy-ester, obtained from the acid (C) on oxidation according to the method of Fieser (*ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4386), did not furnish a keto-ester. The hydroxy-ester on hydrolysis yielded the same lactonic acid (C). Hence, out of the remaining two structures (XII and XIII), the structure (XII) is preferred, avoiding the δ -lactonic structure (XIII) for the acid (C).

The neutral trimethyl ester (IV: R=R₂=Me; R₁=R₄=CO₂Me; R₃=H) underwent the Dieckmann cyclisation with sodium methoxide under nitrogen atmosphere to yield dimethyl δ -methylhydrind- $\Delta^{3,9}$ -en-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (VII: R=R₁=CO₂Me), $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 220 m μ (log ϵ 3.81), in 53-59% yield. When treated with sodium dust the β -keto di-ester was also obtained, but only in 30-35% yield. The ultraviolet spectrum of the β -keto di-ester suggests (Ungnade and Ortega, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 1564) that the double bond is in $\alpha\beta$ -position with respect to the carbomethoxyl group at C₃. It has been reported by Dieckmann (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2470) that ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate exists primarily in the form of the keto derivative (4.5% enol) whereas ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate exists primarily as the enol (76%); in 95% ethanol the values for enolic forms are 5% and 57% respectively as shown by Prelog *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, 34, 1954). These observations definitely excluded the possibility of the above β -keto di-ester to exist in the enolic form (VIII) as the main component. The above β -keto di-ester on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid yielded the keto-acid (IX: R=CO₂H). The double bond of this acid was assumed to migrate in the cyclohexane ring because no ultraviolet absorption maximum in the region 215-220 m μ , characteristic for the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated acids and esters (Ungnade and Ortega, *loc.cit.*), was observed. This phenomenon of double-bond migration from the five-membered ring to the six-membered one, when these are fused together, is in quite agreement with the observations of Brown *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 467) and also that of Dieckmann (*loc.cit.*) as well as of Kon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2727, 3101). The afore-mentioned keto-acid (IX: R=CO₂H) could also be obtained independently from the tri-ester furnished by acid (B).

With the expectation that decarboxylation with base might have preserved the double bond in the cyclopentane ring, attempts were made to eliminate the carbomethoxyl group from the β -keto di-ester with various concentrations of sodium hydroxide and also of barium hydroxide; unfortunately the attempts resulted only in the resinous product. The pure keto-acid (IX: R=CO₂H) under the same conditions of hydrolysis was also converted into similar polymerised product.

During the acid hydrolysis of the β -keto di-ester (VII: R=R₁=CO₂Me) a neutral fraction, having no characteristic absorption in the ultraviolet for the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated

ketone, was obtained in extremely poor yield. This ketonic material on hydrogenation furnished a saturated ketone, the semicarbazone of which melted at 223° and the mixed melting point with the authentic semicarbazone of *cis*-8-methylhydrindanone-1 (XI: $R=R_1=H$) did not show any depression.

The unsaturated keto-acid, 3-carboxy-8-methylhydrind- $\Delta^{4:9}$ -en-1-one (IX: $R=CO_2H$) on catalytic hydrogenation furnished the saturated keto-acid (XI: $R=H$; $R_1=CO_2H$). The latter compound on oxidation with concentrated nitric acid (Bagchi and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1947, **24**, 12) yielded the known *cis*-1-methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid, identified by comparison with an authentic sample prepared according to the method of Linstead and Millidge (*loc. cit.*).

The unsaturated keto-acid (IX: $R=CO_2H$) on pyrolysis was expected to eliminate carbon dioxide with the shift of the double bond to produce the unsaturated ketone (VII: $R=R_1=H$). This type of thermal decarboxylation was studied by Arnold *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4359) and also by Barton and Brooks (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 257). As the thermal decarboxylation of the unsaturated keto-acid (IX: $R=CO_2H$) could not be effected even at 390° - 400° , it was heated with copper-bronze powder in quinoline to furnish the unsaturated ketone (VII: $R=R_1=H$ or IX: $R=H$) which on catalytic hydrogenation afforded *cis*-8-methylhydrindanone-1, identified through its semicarbazone (cf. Bachmann and Raunio, *loc. cit.*; Banerjee and Shafer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 1931; Johnson, *ibid.*, 1944, **66**, 215 and references cited therein).

The trimethyl ester (IV: $R=R_2=Me$; $R_1=R_4=CO_2Me$; $R_3=H$) on hydrogenation by the Adams catalyst yielded the saturated trimethyl ester (XVII) ($R=R_2=Me$; $R_1=R_3=CO_2Me$) which on the Dieckmann cyclisation, followed by the acid hydrolysis, furnished the saturated keto-acid (XI: $R=H$; $R_1=CO_2H$).

The double bond of the β -keto di-ester (VII: $R=R_1=CO_2Me$) is analogous to the $C_{14}-C_{15}$ ethylenic linkage of steroid and might be expected to produce a mixture of *cis* and *trans* compounds on hydrogenation (Johnson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1947, **69**, 2942). But the above compound on catalytic hydrogenation, followed by hydrolysis, yielded the same saturated keto-acid (XI: $R=H$; $R_1=CO_2H$), ring-fusion of which was conclusively proved to be *cis* by oxidation.

(I)

(II)

(III)

* EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2-Methyl-2-carbethoxycyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetate (II: R = Me; R₁ = CO₂Et) and *Imide of 2-Methyl-2-carboxycyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetic Acid* (III).—Ethyl cyano-

All m.p.s are uncorrected. The UV-spectrum was measured by the Unicam spectrophotometer SP. 500.

acetate (115 c.c.), ethyl 2-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (115 g.), glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.), ammonium acetate (12 g.) and dry benzene (250 c.c.) were refluxed in a flask, to which a water separator had been attached, until no further water separated. Further ammonium acetate (12 g.) was added and the refluxing was continued; the process was repeated until the quantity of ammonium acetate amounted to 60 g. The mixture was refluxed for a total period of 30 hours. It was cooled, when a yellow solid (III), m.p. 226° (decomp.), separated out, yield 15 g. The solid was filtered and the crystalline mass was recrystallised 4 times from ethanol to furnish pure white crystals, m.p. 230-31° (decomp.); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{10}$ 220m μ (log ϵ 4.026). (Found: C, 64.64; H, 6.15; N, 13.78. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires C, 64.70; H, 5.88; N, 13.72%).

The dark brown filtrate was washed with water and the solvent was removed. Distillation of the residual oil gave a slightly viscous oil, b.p. 165-68°/1mm; η_{D}^{26} 1.4762, yield 107 g. (Lit. b.p. 160-65°/11mm).

Diethyl α -Cyano- α -(2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclohex- $\Delta^1:6$ -enyl)-succinate (IV: R=Me; R₁=R₄=CO₂Et; R₂=Et; R₃=CN).—Sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (5.75 g.) and absolute ethanol (200 c.c.), was cooled to 0°-5° for 30 minutes. To it the above cyano-ester (70 g.) was added dropwise with constant shaking; immediately the colour of the solution was changed to brown. The temperature of the alcoholic solution was maintained at 0°-5° for 1 hour more with frequent shaking. To this sodio-enolate ethyl bromoacetate (48 g.) was added all at a time and the reaction mixture was immediately refluxed on the water-bath for 16 hours. It was cooled, diluted with water and extracted 4 times with a mixture of ether and benzene. The extract was then washed twice with water. After removal of the solvent, a thick viscous oil was obtained, b.p. 195-200°/1mm, η_{D}^{25} 1.4780, yield 77.0 g. (Found: C, 62.34; H, 7.86. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 62.46; H, 7.39%).

Hydrolysis of the above Succinate (IV: R=Me; R₁=R₄=CO₂Et; R₂=Et; R₃=CN).—(a). A mixture of the above succinate (58 g.) and HCl (conc., 650 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 36 hours. Most of the HCl was removed and after dilution with ice-cold water the organic acidic material was extracted thoroughly with ether. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and after removal of the solvent a viscous liquid was obtained. On attempting crystallisation from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) a solid acid (8.0 g.), m.p. 130-45°, separated out. This acid was dissolved in a mixture of ethyl acetate (25 c.c.), dry ether (200 c.c.) and petroleum ether (50 c.c.) and the resulting solution was allowed to stand at room temperature for 7 days when the lactonic dicarboxylic acid (B), m.p. 182°, separated out; yield 3.2 g. This was recrystallised 3 times from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether to afford the pure material, m.p. 184-85°. (Found: C, 56.01; H, 6.40; N.E., 130. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 56.25; H, 6.25%; N.E., 128).

From the mother-liquor the tricarboxylic acid (A), m.p. 148-50°, was obtained; yield 6.8 g. Two further crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether furnished the pure acid, m.p. 152-53°. (Found: C, 56.40; H, 6.45; N.E., 86. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 56.25; H, 6.25%; N.E., 85.3).

(b). Again, when a mixture of the above succinate (58 g.) and HCl (conc., 600 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 55 hours and the hydrolysed product was extracted as before,

it yielded a viscous liquid. This was dissolved in a mixture of ether and petroleum ether (6 : 1) and the resulting solution was allowed to stand for 18 hours at room temperature when the lactonic monocarboxylic acid (C) crystallised out, m.p. 190-92°, yield 4.6 g. Four crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether afforded the pure acid, m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 62.38; H, 7.15; N.E., 213. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 62.27; H, 7.54%; N.E., 212).

Esterification of the Crude Acids.—After removal of the solid lactonic acid (C), as stated above in (b), the remaining curde gummy acid mixture was esterified by refluxing with a mixture of dry methanol (250 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (d 1.84, 35 c.c.) for 50 hours. The mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice when a heavy oil separated out. It was repeatedly extracted with ether-benzene mixture. The extract was successively washed with water, ice-cold 5% NaOH solution and finally with water. The solvents were removed. Distillation of the residual oil furnished a yellow mobile liquid (IV: $R=R_2=Me$; $R_1=R_4=CO_2Me$; $R_3=H$), b.p. 155-60°/0.8 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4819, yield 29.5g. (Found: C, 60.50; H, 7.52. $C_{12}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 60.39; H, 7.38 %).

The same ester was obtained from the acid (A) in excellent yield by means of diazomethane. Saponification of this ester with 20% methanolic KOH solution afforded the tricarboxylic acid (A).

The alkaline aqueous layer was acidified with HCl (dil.) and the precipitated oil was extracted with ether-benzene mixture to furnish the ester of the lactonic dicarboxylic acid (B), b.p. 160-62°/0.5 mm, yield 1.8 g. (Found: C, 59.18; H, 7.37. $C_{14}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 59.15; H, 7.04 %). The same ester was obtained from the acid (B) by means of diazomethane. Hydrolysis of this ester with HCl (conc.) furnished the acid (B).

The methyl ester of the lactonic monocarboxylic acid (C) was prepared by treating the cold ethereal solution of the acid (C) (2.12 g.) with an ethereal solution of diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethyl urea (1.8 g.) and allowing the reaction to proceed for 20 minutes. After decomposition of the excess of diazomethane with acetic acid, the reaction mixture was worked up as usual and evaporatively distilled at 140-45°/0.8 mm, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 64.12; H, 7.73. $C_{12}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 63.71; H, 7.96%).

Interconversions of the Acids.—(a). A mixture of acid (A) (1 g.) and HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 10 hours. Fresh HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) was added and the mixture was refluxed for another 10 hours. After working up as before, the residue was crystallised from dilute methanol to furnish the pure acid, m.p. 184-85°, yield 0.1 g. Mixed m.p. with the lactonic dicarboxylic acid (B), obtained before, was 183-84°.

(b). A mixture of the acid (A) (2 g.) and HCl (conc., 30 c.c.) was refluxed for 30 hours. After addition of fresh HCl (conc., 15 c.c.), the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 15 hours. After working up, the residue was crystallised thrice from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether to afford the pure acid, m.p. 200°, yield 0.026 g. On admixture with lactonic monocarboxylic acid (C), obtained before, the m.p. remained undepressed.

(c) Similarly, when a mixture of lactonic dicarboxylic acid (B) (2.5 g.) and HCl (conc., 40 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 30 hours, it yielded a gummy acid which on evaporative distillation at 150-60°/1 mm furnished the lactonic monocarboxylic acid, m.p. 199-200°; yield 0.673 g. Mixed m.p. with the previous sample was 200°.

Dimethyl 8-Methylhydrind- $\Delta^{3:9}$ -en-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (VII: R = R₁ = CO₂Me).—

(a). To the sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium dust (1.57 g.) and methanol (2.8 c.c.) in dry benzene (30 c.c.), was added the neutral ester (10.3 g.) in dry benzene (40 c.c.). The mixture was then refluxed for 4-5 hours under nitrogen atmosphere. The solution was cooled under nitrogen and acidified with cold HCl (dil.). The organic layer was washed successively with water, ice-cold 5% aqueous KOH solution and finally with water. After removal of the solvent, the β -keto di-ester was distilled at 165-68°/1.5 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4935, λ_{max}^{alc} 220 m μ (log ϵ 3.81), yield 5.30 g. (Found: C, 63.41; H, 6.40. C₁₄H₁₈O₃ requires C, 63.15; H, 6.76%).

(b). To a suspension of sodium dust (1.57 g.) in dry benzene (25 c.c.) was added a solution of trimethyl ester (10.03 g.) in dry benzene (40 c.c.) containing 5 drops of methanol. The mixture was then refluxed for 4 hours. The dark red solution containing solid suspension of the sodio-enolate was cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The β -keto di-ester, after working up as before, was distilled, yield 2.8 g.

3-Carboxy-8-methylhydrind- $\Delta^{4:9}$ -en-1-one (IX: R = CO₂H).—(a). A mixture of the above β -keto di-ester (20.5 g.) and HCl (conc., 100 c.c.) was refluxed for 32 hours. The cooled solution, after dilution with ice-water, was repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was then extracted 4 times with cold 5% aqueous NaOH solution, washed with water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and after removal of the solvent a neutral ketone (0.28 g.), having strong camphoraceous odour and no characteristic absorption in the ultraviolet region for the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl grouping, was obtained.

The combined alkaline extract was acidified with HCl (dil.) and the precipitated oil was extracted several times with ether. After removal of the ether, the gummy keto-acid (10.2 g.) was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether to afford the pure material, m.p. 160°. (Found: C, 68.45; H, 7.58; N.E., 196. C₁₁H₁₄O₃ requires C, 68.04; H, 7.21%; N.E., 194).

The *semicarbazone* of the keto-acid, prepared by the pyridine method, after purification by crystallisation from dilute methanol, melted at 258° (decomp.). (Found: C, 57.20; H, 7.11. C₁₂H₁₇O₃N₃ requires C, 57.37; H, 6.77%).

(b). A solution of the β -keto di-ester (3.25 g.) in acetic acid (6 c.c.) and 6N-HCl (25 c.c.) was allowed to reflux for 16 hours. After working up as before, the residual gummy acidic material was evaporatively distilled at 110-15°/1.5 mm. The yellow semisolid distillate was crystallised as before, yielding the keto-acid (1.51 g.), m.p. 159-60°.

(c). A solution of the β -keto di-ester (1.85 g.) in a mixture of 48% HBr (6 c.c.), acetic acid (9 c.c.) and water (3 c.c.) was refluxed for 5 hours at 130° in an oil-bath. After removal of the acetic and hydrobromic acids the residual gummy material was worked up as before when the keto-acid (0.8 g.) was obtained as a thick oil which solidified completely after 4 days. Two crystallisations afforded a pure material, m.p. 159-60°.

(d). *From Lactonic Dicarboxylic Acid (B)*.—To the solution of sodium (0.23 g.), dissolved in dry methanol (5 c.c.), was added a solution of the lactonic dicarboxylic acid (B) (1.15 g.) in methanol (5 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hours on a

water-bath, cooled and then treated in the cold with methyl iodide (5 c.c.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 hours. Most of the methanol was distilled and the resulting liquid was poured into ice-water containing HCl (conc., 5 c.c.). The precipitated oil was extracted five times with ether. The combined ether extract was washed successively with ice-water, cold 5% aqueous NaOH solution (15 c.c.) and finally with water. After removal of the solvent, a neutral ester was obtained as a mobile yellow liquid, b.p. 155°/0.8 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4810, yield 0.83 g. (Found: C, 59.81; H, 7.63. $C_{15}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 60.39; H, 7.38%). The neutral tri-ester on the Dieckmann cyclisation with sodium methoxide, followed by acid hydrolysis, yielded the same unsaturated keto-acid, m.p. 160°, as obtained above.

3-Carbomethoxy-8-methylhydrind- $\Delta^{4,5}$ -en-1-one (IX: R = CO₂Me).—The methyl ester of the above keto-acid was prepared by treating the cold ethereal solution of the keto-acid (2 g.) with an ethereal solution of diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethyl urea (2 g.) and allowing the reaction to proceed for 15 minutes. After working up as usual, the residue was evaporatively distilled at 120-25°/1.5 mm, yield 1.7 g. (Found: C, 68.95; H, 7.94. $C_{12}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 69.23; H, 7.69%).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared by the pyridine method, was crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 220° (decomp.). (Found: C, 59.22; H, 7.38. $C_{15}H_{18}O_5N_2$ requires C, 58.87; H, 7.17%).

Methyl β -Carbomethoxy-(β -2-methyl-2-carbomethoxycyclohexyl)-propionate (XVII: R = R₂ = Me; R₁ = R₃ = CO₂Me).—To a suspension of pre-reduced PtO₂ catalyst (0.13 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) was added a solution of the unsaturated tri-ester (8 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The theoretical amount of hydrogen (650 c.c.) was absorbed in 56 hours. After working up as usual, the residual oil on distillation gave a colorless mobile liquid, b. p. 155-57°/1 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4715, yield 7.8 g. (Found: C, 60.23; H, 8.41. $C_{15}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0%).

cis-Dimethyl 8-Methylhydrindan-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (XI: R = R₁ = CO₂Me).—To the sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium dust (0.8 g.) and methanol (1.3 c.c.) in dry benzene (200 c.c.), was added a solution of the above saturated tri-ester (7.8 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere for 4 hours. After working up as before, the residual liquid on distillation yielded a colorless oil, b.p. 135-40°/0.5 mm, yield 4.0 g. (Found: C, 62.50; H, 7.50. $C_{14}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 62.69; H, 7.46%).

cis-8-Methylhydrindan-1-one-3-carboxylic Acid (XI: R = H; R₁ = CO₂H).—(a). To a pre-reduced suspension of PtO₂ catalyst (0.05 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added a solution of the unsaturated keto-acid (0.5 g.), m.p. 160°, in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The theoretical amount of hydrogen (50 c.c.) was absorbed within 2 hours. Then it was filtered and most of the acetic acid was distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was cooled, diluted with ice-water and extracted 4 times with ether. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and distilled. The gummy acid on keeping in the refrigerator solidified. Three crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether afforded

the pure material, m.p. 155-56° yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 67.38; H, 8.22. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 67.34; H, 8.16%). The keto-acid (IX: R = CO₂H) and its ester, however, could not be reduced by 10% Pd-C in alcoholic solution.

(b). A mixture of the above saturated β -keto di-ester (XI: R = R₁ = CO₂Me; 3.5 g.) and HCl (conc., 35 c.c.) was refluxed for 20 hours. On working up as before, the residue was evaporatively distilled at 110-15°/1 mm, yield 2.0 g. The semisolid distillate was crystallised thrice from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether to afford the pure material, m.p. 153-54°. The m.p. was undepressed on admixture of the same acid obtained before.

(c). To a suspension of 10% Pd-C (0.5 g.) in 95% ethanol (10 c.c.) was added a solution of the dimethyl 8-methylhydrind- $\Delta^{3:9}$ -en-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (2 g.) in 95% ethanol (10 c.c.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The theoretical amount of hydrogen (170 c.c.) was absorbed within 5 hours. Then it was filtered and worked up as before. Distillation gave a colorless oil, b.p. 135-40°/0.6 mm, yield 1.8 g. This on hydrolysis with HCl (conc.) for 20 hours yielded the same saturated keto-acid, m.p. 153°.

Methyl cis-8-Methylhydrindan-1-one-3-carboxylate (XI: R = H; R₁ = CO₂Me).—The above saturated keto-acid (1 g.) was esterified with diazomethane in cold ethereal solution. After working up as before, the residual oil was evaporatively distilled at 120°/0.9 mm, yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 68.37; H, 8.64. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57%).

The semicarbazone, prepared and purified as before, melted at 192-93°. (Found: C, 58.3; H, 8.0. $C_{13}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires C, 58.42; H, 7.86%).

cis-1-Methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic Acid.—The keto-acid (XI: R = H; R₁ = CO₂H; 1.38 g.) was heated with nitric acid (d 1.4, 9 c.c.) on a boiling water-bath for 1 hour. It was then refluxed with addition of water (8 c.c.) for further 1½ hours. The solution was evaporated as much as possible (about 10 c.c.) on the water-bath and then left in an evacuated desiccator containing solid KOH when the dicarboxylic acid (0.3 g.) separated out, m.p. 153°. It was thrice recrystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether when the pure acid, m.p. 160°, was obtained. (Found: C, 57.86; H, 7.60. Calc. for $C_8H_{14}O_4$: C, 58.06; H, 7.52%).

cis-8-Methylhydrindanone-1 (XI: R = R₁ = H).—(a). To a suspension of 10% Pd-C (0.05 g.) in 95% ethanol (10 c.c.) was added a solution of the unsaturated neutral ketone (0.27 g.), obtained from the hydrolysis of the β -keto di-ester, in 95% ethanol (10 c.c.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The uptake of hydrogen (40 c.c.) was very fast. It was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated. To this concentrated solution was added semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.3 g.) and pyridine (0.5 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed for 5 minutes. After cooling, the alcoholic solution was diluted with water when white crystals of the semicarbazone (0.2 g.) of *cis-8-methylhydrindanone-1*, m.p. 195-200°, was obtained; three crystallisations from dilute methanol afforded pure semicarbazone, m.p. 223° (bath temp. 200°). The mixed m.p. with the authentic sample was 222-23° (bath temp. 200°). (Found: C, 63.02; H, 9.02; N, 19.42. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{18}ON_3$: C, 63.15; H, 9.09; N, 20.09%).

(b). A mixture of 3-carboxy-8-methylhydrind- $\Delta^{4,9}$ -en-1-one (0.8 g.), m.p. 156-57°, copper-bronze powder (0.1 g.) and dry quinoline (5 c.c.) was heated under reflux in an oil-bath (bath temp. 250°-270°) for 13 hours. The mixture was cooled, diluted with ether (50 c.c.) and filtered. The filtrate was washed successively with 6N-HCl (20 c.c.), sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The neutral fraction, evaporatively distilled at 100-105°/25 mm, was hydrogenated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.1 g.) in 95% ethanol (20 c.c.). The uptake of hydrogen (42 c.c.) was very fast. After filtration, the solution was concentrated and the ketone was converted into semi-carbazone, m.p. 223°. The mixed m.p. with the authentic sample was 223° (bath temp. 200°).

(c). A mixture of the unsaturated keto-acid (1.2 g.), m.p. 160°, pyridine (6 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 24 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 2 hours according to the method of Johnson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2942). No decarboxylation was effected and the original acid was recovered.

(d). The unsaturated keto-acid, m.p. 160°, was heated at 255°-270° and 390°-400° respectively for 24 hours without isolation of the expected unsaturated ketone, but some unchanged material could be recovered.

β -Carbomethoxy- β -(2-methylcyclohexenyl)-propionic Acid (XV: R=H).—To an ice-cold solution of potassium *tert.*-butoxide, prepared from potassium (4.3 g.) and dry *tert.*-butyl alcohol (100 c.c.), was added a mixture of 2-methylcyclohexanone (11.2 g.) and dimethyl succinate (22 g.) in *tert.*-butyl alcohol (20 c.c.) with constant shaking. The brownish red solution was heated under reflux for 60 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen and then kept at room temperature for 4 hours. Acidification with ice-cold 6N-HCl afforded a straw-yellow solution which was concentrated under reduced pressure. Sufficient water was added to the cold solution which was extracted 4 times with ether-benzene mixture. The solvent layer was thoroughly extracted with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and the bicarbonate solution after acidification with cold dilute hydrochloric acid was extracted 5 times with ether-benzene mixture. After removal of the solvent, the half-ester was distilled, b.p. 145-50°/0.5 mm, yield 15.8 g. (Found: C, 64.00; H, 7.82. $C_{12}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 63.71; H, 7.96%).

α -(2-Methylcyclohexyl)-succinic Acid (XIV: R=R₁=H).—(a). The half-ester (4.3 g.) was esterified with diazomethane in cold ethereal solution. After decomposition of the excess of diazomethane, the methyl ester, worked up as before, was distilled, b.p. 125-27°/4 mm, yield 3.6 g. This di-ester (3.6 g.) was reduced in glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) in presence of platinum oxide (0.2 g.). The theoretical amount of hydrogen (350 c.c.) was absorbed within 7 hours. It was filtered, worked up as before, and distilled, b.p. 125-26°/4 mm, yield 2.95 g. Saponification of the above saturated di-ester (1.2 g.) was effected with 10% methanolic NaOH solution (20 c.c.). After 6 hours' refluxing methanol was removed completely. The residue after dilution with ice-water was acidified and the precipitated oil was repeatedly extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed once with saturated brine solution and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removal of the solvent, the acid (0.95 g.), m.p. 134-38°, containing adhering gum, was crystallised thrice from a mixture of ether and petroleum

ether to afford pure acid, m.p. 155°. The mixed m.p. of this acid with that of the dicarboxylic acid obtained from the lactonic monocarboxylic acid (c) did not show any depression. (Found: C, 61.91; H, 8.00. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 61.68; H, 8.41%).

(b). *From the Lactonic Monocarboxylic Acid (C)*.—To the solution of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (0.092 g.) and methanol (4 c.c.), was added a solution of lactonic monocarboxylic acid (C: 0.424 g.), m.p. 200°, in dry methanol (14 c.c.). The reaction mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours, cooled and then methyl iodide (2 c.c.) was added to it. It was allowed to reflux for 6 hours. After removal of methanol, the residue was diluted with water and worked up as described in previous experiment. After removal of the solvent, the hydroxy-ester was evaporatively distilled at 110-12°/0.2-0.3 mm, yield 0.45 g. (Found: C, 60.17; H, 8.74. $C_{13}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 60.46; H, 8.53%). To a solution of the hydroxy-ester (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added a solution of sodium dichromate (1.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) and dry benzene (15 c.c.). The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours and then worked up as usual, but no keto-ester was obtained. The hydroxy-ester on hydrolysis with 10% methanolic NaOH solution, followed by acidification, yielded the same lactonic acid, m.p. 199-200°. An intimate mixture of the hydroxy-ester (0.45 g.) and fused potassium hydrogen sulphate (1.5 g.), taken in a sublimation tube, was introduced into the air chamber, previously heated to 180° and kept at that temperature for 1 hour under nitrogen. The dehydrated product was allowed to evaporatively distil at 80°-100°/0.1 mm. The sublimate was taken up in ether and the ethereal layer was washed successively with ice-water, ice-cold 5% aqueous NaOH solution and ice-water, and then dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . After removal of the ether, the unsaturated di-ester was evaporatively distilled at 90°-100°/0.2 mm, yield 0.27 g. (Found: C, 64.80; H, 7.89. $C_{13}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 65.00; H, 8.33%).

To a suspension of pre-reduced PtO_2 catalyst (0.1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added a solution of the above unsaturated di-ester (1.6 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The theoretical amount of hydrogen (150 c.c.) was absorbed within 3 hours. Then it was filtered from the catalyst and worked up as before. The saturated di-ester was evaporatively distilled at 110-15°/0.4 mm, yield 1.25. (Found: C, 64.35; H, 9.10. $C_{13}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 64.46; H, 9.09%).

A mixture of the above di-ester (1.18 g.) and HCl (conc., 12 c.c.) was refluxed for 8 hours. It was diluted with ice-water and worked up as before. The residue, after four crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether, afforded the pure acid, m.p. 155-56°, yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 61.34; H, 8.21. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 61.68; H, 8.41%).

Diethyl α -Cyano- α -(2-methylcyclohex- $\Delta^{1:8}$ -enyl)-succinate (IV: R=Me; R_1 =H; R_2 =Et; R_3 =CO₂Et; R_4 =CN).—To the cold solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (2.3 g.) in absolute ethanol (100 c.c.), was added ethyl 2 methylcyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetate (II: R=Me; R_1 =H; 19.4 g.) dropwise with shaking under the conditions described before. Ethyl bromoacetate (17 g.) was added all at a time and refluxed on a water-bath for 8-10 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and

after dilution with water the material was worked up as before. After removal of the solvent, the succinic ester was distilled, b.p. 168-75°/1 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4740, yield 17.6 g. (Found: C, 65.68; H, 8.16. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4N$ requires C, 65.48; H, 7.90%).

γ -(2-Methylcyclohexyl)- β -carboxy-spirobutyrolactone (V: R=Me; R_1 =H; R_2 =CO₂H).—(a). A mixture of the above succinate (6.8 g.) and HCl (conc., 125 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 16 hours. The resulting mixture was diluted with water and after saturation with common salt the acidic layer was extracted with ether. Ether extract was washed with brine solution and dried. After removal of the solvent the crude solid acid, m.p. 98-101°, containing adhering gum, was obtained; yield 2.1 g. Three crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether afforded the pure acid, m.p. 107°. (Found: C, 62.07; H, 7.64; N.E., 21.4. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 62.27; H, 7.5%; N.E., 21.2).

(b). A mixture of the above half-ester (XV: R=H; 2.3 g.) and HCl (conc., 20 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 24 hours. On evaporation of HCl the crude lactonic acid (2 g.), m.p. 104-105°, was crystallised twice from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether to afford the pure acid, m.p. 107°.

γ -(2-Methylcyclohexyl)-spirobutyrolactone (V: R=Me; R_1 = R_2 =H).—An intimate mixture of the solid lactonic acid (2.55 g.) and powdered glass (3 g.), taken in a 25 c.c. Vigreux column Claisen flask, was heated in a metal bath at 240°-250° and kept at that temperature for 80 minutes, when there was practically no evidence of any reaction. It was distilled, b.p. 130-35°/4 mm, yield 1.73 g. The above lactone was taken up in ether which was successively washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled, yield 1.60 g. (Found: C, 71.22; H, 9.01. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$: C, 71.44; H, 9.52%).

2-Methyl-2-carboxycyclohex- $\Delta^{1,2}$ -enyl-1-acetic Acid (XVI).—A mixture of the imide of 2-methyl-2-carboxycyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetic acid (III: 1.1 g.) and 20% aqueous NaOH (20 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 56 hours when the evolution of ammonia had completely ceased. On acidification the dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 157-59°, separated out, yield 0.43 g. Three crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether afforded the pure acid, m.p. 169°. (Found: C, 60.50; H, 7.24. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{14}O_4$: C, 60.60; H, 7.07%). Mixed m.p. with the authentic sample of the acid, prepared as follows, was 169-70°.

Ethyl 2-methyl-2-carbethoxycyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetate (1 g.) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 20 c.c.) for 24 hours. The acid was worked up with ether as before and on recrystallisation for 4 times from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether furnished the pure acid, m.p. 169-70°.

Grateful thanks of the authors are due to Messrs. East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., for awarding a fellowship to one of them (R. C. C.). Thanks are also due to Prof. Dr. W. S. Johnson of the Wisconsin University, U. S. A., for supplying the authentic semicarbazone of *cis*-8-methylhydrindan-1-one.